

Three cohorts ...

... and their pathway to Responsible Research and Innovation via crowdsourcing

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Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Who? RRI groups

Source: <http://www.rri-tools.eu>

How? RRI process dimensions

Where? Cohort regions

What? Key aspects

- Address societal challenges
- Align with societal values, needs and expectations
- Open to all actors and at all levels

Our Vision and Ambitions

Our vision

We want people to live better and healthier lives thanks to trust, understanding, and engagement in science.

Our ambitions

- To engage citizens in a more co-creative manner
- To promote equal access to science
- To promote innovation and engagement

Present our Roadmap

- Crowdsourcing concept
- Web-platform
- Communication, dissemination and engagement
- Institutional changes
- Evaluation strategies

Methods: Three cohorts

Cohort project	Country	Cohort	Start	n	Response (%)
Study of Health in Pomerania (SHIP)	Germany	SHIP	1997	4,308	68.8
		TREND	2003	4,420	50.1
		NEXT	2021	[4,400]	na ^a
Bialystok Polish Longitudinal University Study (PLUS)	Poland	PLUS	2018	637	45.4 ^b
Rotterdam Study (RS)	Netherlands	RS-I	1989	7,983	78.1
		RS-II	1999	3,011	67.3
		RS-III	2006	3,932	64.9
		RS-IV	2016	3,368	46
Total				27,659	

^a Ongoing; started in 2021 (target: 4400 participants until 2026)

^b Ongoing; started in 2019

Platform: Community-based and –driven

Targeted communication and dissemination

Targeted communications

... also in local languages ...

... in different formats ...

Online

- Web page
- Social media
- Newsletters

Offline

- Newspaper
- Radio
- Press release

... with the aim to move

from a **deficit** to a **dialogue** framework!

Engagement approaches: Management cycles

- More than a loose network
- Each cohort chooses featured topic every 3 months

C: 1st cycle of management block; 1 cycle = 1 month

1 block = 3 cycles = 1 **mini-experiment**

Apply, design and evaluate best practices:

- RRI, systems thinking
- co-creation
- mutual learning
- evaluation, etc.

Road map of institutional changes

Conclusions: Soften / connect bubbles

Evaluation strategies

Concept

Each month = start of 3-month experiment

1 block = 3 cycles = 1 mini-experiment

Response

Study invitation with/-out info on JoinUs4Health

■ Control group (without)

■ Intervention group (with)

--> group comparison

Attitude, skills

Cohort participants
(population sample)

↔

Platform users
(population sample)

3 countries

Overall project

Integrated approaches to health

Network for Evaluation of One Health A handbook for the evaluation of One Health

In discussion

Access and combine diverse knowledge sources

Level	Outcomes
Societal practice	New formats of engagement, innovation, mutual learning, ...
Scientific practice	Generic insights, new methodology, ...
Transdisciplinary process	New knowledge and understanding

Ruegg et al (2018): Front Vet Sci 5(23) / Handbook for the evaluation of One Health

These approaches may

- make research more sensitive to societal expectations and concerns and
- enhance citizens' preparedness to participate

JoinUs4Health: Next steps

- Pilot testing of processes and platform (Oct/21-Jan/22)
- Public access to platform (Jan/21)

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Thank you!

Get in touch if you want to engage,
receive updates or share comments /
experiences

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